

TOWARDS A NOVEL FRAMEWORK OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR FOR MEASURING THE IMPACTS OF SMART CITIES IN EMERGING ECONOMIES

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Abstract: Smart Cities take advantage of innovative technologies to improve city-administration, increase the level of interactivity and improve the quality of life of citizens in a community. An important question is whether cities are truly measured in their policies and practices relative to any proposed model. Based on focus-group interview supplemented by an aspect of Q-methodology, this paper investigates how stakeholders prioritize the factors/indicators of cities smartness in the context of Abuja city. The paper addresses the challenges of quantifying the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) needed to monitor the impacts of smartness in emerging economies. To propose a novel framework model, the study analyse the existing models and frameworks for measuring the impacts of Smart Cities with a view to identifying the core indicators that will be unique for cities in emerging economies. The analysis shows that the existing models focused on the identification of indicators of economy, people, governance, environment, mobility, and living. However, the study found that core indicators on infrastructure are omitted. The paper therefore propose collapsing the well-known indicators into three core components of smart cities, namely Smart infrastructure, smart institution and the smart people to have a more holistic assessment of smart cities impacts.

Keywords: Smart Cities, KPIs, Emerging Economies, Smart Infrastructure, Smart Institutions, Smart People.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many cities are transitioning from traditional cities into Smart Cities and a main motivation for this trend is because of their perceived ability to improve the standard of living of the people residing in such cities. However, in order to justify this assertion it is necessary to identify some relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through which we can analyze their impact. A number of research efforts have focused on the development of such indicators and many of their derived KPIs are already in use today.

A systematic literature review of such prior research shows that many of the KPIs were developed with the assumption that they would be implemented in developed countries, which already have the relevant amenities and infrastructure. However, this assumption does not hold for developing economies, where many amenities and basic infrastructure are lacking. The examples cited in the analysis are illustrations of potential aspirational and practical solutions that are already realized in advanced economies such as USA.

This research aims to bridge this knowledge gap by proposing a list of KPIs that can be readily used in emerging cities in a developing country context. In particular, the study have derived KPIs that take the infrastructure problems in developing countries into account. Hence in order to elicit knowledge from professionals that will assist in developing a simple

and adoptable model of measurement, this study adopted Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja focusing on key stakeholders in academia, ICT industry, and the City Administration as case study. FCT-Abuja is a typical emerging city in an emerging economy embarking on laudable Smart City initiatives (Jiriko, JY et al. 2015). The focus group interview with FCT Abuja Smart City stakeholders adopted an aspect of Q methodology that grouped the core components of Smart Cities into three (3) distinct components of smart infrastructure, smart institutions, and smart people respectively. Q methodology invented by William Stevphen (a British physicist/psychologist), permits the systematic study of subjectivity and communicating the subjective perceptions of the participants point of view central to its investigative procedures (Du Plessis 2005).

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: section 2 gives the theoretical background and relevant literature review. Section 3, presents the proposed KPIs for measuring the smartness of cities and discuss the theoretical framework extensively while section 4 gives an overview of the methodology used for this work. Section 5 summarizes the result of the focus group (experts' interviews) leading to the proposed Smart Cities KPIs and section 6 gives a conclusion to the paper and discusses the proposed future work.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Smart City Definition

Smart Cities represent an emerging area of research that is gaining a lot of attention. A number of definitions have been proposed and one such notable definitions was given by Forrester, who defined a Smart City as 'the use of smart computing technologies to make the critical infrastructure components and services of a city – which include city administration, education, healthcare, public safety, real estate, transportation, and utilities – more intelligent, interconnected, and efficient' (Washburn, Sindhu et al. 2009). Similarly, IBM (2009) gave a definition from an industry point of view- 'a Smarter City uses technology to transform its core systems and optimize resources. At the highest levels of maturity, a Smarter City is a knowledge-based system that provides real-time insights to stakeholders, as well as enabling decision-makers to proactively manage the city's subsystems. Effective information management is at the heart of this capability, and integration and analytics are seen as the key enablers' (ITU 2014).

According to Gartner as cited by Lee, Hancock et al. (2014) 'a Smart City is based on intelligent exchange of information that flow between its many different subsystems. This flow of information is analyzed and translated into citizen and commercial services. The city will act on this information flow to make its wider ecosystem more resource-efficient and sustainable. The information exchange is based on a smart governance operating framework designed for sustainable cities. The authors posited that Smart City is a concept that derives its definition from a combination of 'information city, knowledge city, intelligent city, ubiquitous city, and digital city'. After critical evaluation of different characteristics of the Smart City concept, these authors concluded that 'Smart Cities are envisioned as creating a better, more sustainable city, in which people's quality of life is higher, their environment more livable and their economic prospects stronger'.

In addition, Harrisson C. as cited in Chourabi, Nam et al. (2012) considered Smart City as the city connecting the physical infrastructure, the IT infrastructure, the social infrastructure, and the business infrastructure to leverage the collective intelligence of the city. According to

Batty, Axhausen et al. (2012), Smart Cities are simply ‘instruments for improving competitiveness in such a way that community and quality of life are enhanced’. The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) during its focused group analysis (ITU 2014) and in an effort to come up with a standardized definition for Smart and Sustainable Cities, analyzed over 100 publications and this gave different definitions of Smart Cities. From ITU’s analysis, the over 100 definitions of ‘Smart City’ kept revolving around 50 keywords like quality of life, ICT, Technology, innovations, management, systems, integrate, intelligent, etc., where the instance of about 726 of those keywords were analyzed to measure or compare the importance of those words on the subject matter.

In summary, the issue of improved services and quality of life are considered imperative in a Smart City. Thus, the concept of Smart City has the central objective of improving quality of life in today’s densely populated cities around the globe socially, politically, culturally, and economically with equal access devoid of any form of exclusion in terms of time and location. Hence, it is crucial for Smart Cities to create knowledge, as well as transfer knowledge, social innovations and a host of other services using the emerging technologies in Cloud Computing as a platform for solving environmental, ecological, social, and sustainability problems facing the ever-expanding cities today.

2.2 Smart Cities Standardization and the Framework for Measurement

A couple of Smart City scholarships have discussed the issue of standardization and the metrics for monitoring cities development from different perspectives. For instance, City Protocol (2015) developed an interesting hierarchical model for city governance, evaluation, and transformation. The City Protocol model incorporated the original City Anatomy CPA-I 001 body of knowledge, Anatomy Indicators CPA-PR 002, Anatomy Ontology CPAPR 003, and Livable District CPC 004, etc. It is important to note that every city in different regions of the world is unique with different development challenges depending on their experiences and history. In this context, while some cities are dealing with challenges of environmental pollution, others are faced with congestion, energy, and security related issues (Ceballos and Larios 2016). However, because of the interrelationship that exists amongst the indicators of Smart City systems, a number of standards have been proposed for monitoring performance of cities smartness. The existing standards include ISO-37120 standard for Sustainable Development and Resilience of Communities –Global City Indicators for Service and Quality of Life, ISO-37101 Sustainable Development and Resilience Communities –Management Systems, ITU Smart Sustainable Cities, Spanish Standards (AENOR) –UNE 178301 on Open Data and UNE 178303 Requirements for Municipal’s Asset Management, NIST – Internet of Things (IoT) Enabled Smart City Framework, etc.

The ISO 37120 standard for instance, established 46 core indicators and 54 supporting indicators for measuring smartness (Hernandez 2014). According to Hernandez (2014), the ISO-37120 indicators are applicable to any city and it can serve as tools for City Mayors, Urban planners, researchers, professionals and other stakeholders for benchmarking investment, building smart sustainable cities, impacts evaluation, comparison, and measuring effectiveness of city governance, etc. Overall, ISO-37120 standard introduces methodologies in the form of indicators for measuring performance of services in cities especially in the area of quality of life with a matrix that attempts to reveal key technologies that underpin many Smart Cities initiatives today. On the other hand, ITU introduced standard specification for Smart Sustainable cities. As revealed by Anthopoulos and Giannakidis (2016), the ITU

standard for Smart Sustainable Cities defines a set of primary smart services for cities. Further, the standard introduced a technical report that can form the basis for global Smart Sustainable City that can afterward, be adopted for developing a framework for measuring performance of Smart Cities (ITU, 2014).

At the sub-regional level, Spanish standard (AENOR) have adopted the ISO-37120, which correspond to its standardization efforts to introduce the UNE-178301 and UNE 178303 respectively. The Spanish standards address Open Data standardization and requirements for municipal asset's management. Similarly, in the USA the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) embarked on a couple of Smart City related standards which include Internet of Things (IoT) Enabled Smart City Framework standard in an attempt to enhance interoperability of Smart City technologies across cities with cost effectiveness and convergence that will serve the global Smart City needs (NIST 2016). The NIST IoT standard was developed in collaboration with ANSI, MISPA ITIA and ETSI. For further information on existing Smart City standard, see (Zdraveski et al., 2017, Lombardi et al., 2012, ISO IEC 2014, BSI 2014).

The standard defined in ISO-37120 above identified 17 key areas of measures with 100 indicators. In practice, Cohen (2015) proposed a Smart City model for measuring city performance with six dimensions i.e. Smart Economy, Smart Environment, Smart People, Smart Governance, Smart Mobility, and Smart Living (Cohen 2012). Cohen's model was based on ranking and benchmarking approaches using indicator average of the six dimensions of Smart Cities. The model relied on secondary data from different sources which includes IDC rankings of Smart Cities in Spain, Siemens Green City Index, Global Metro Monitor, and a host of international organisations (Benamrou et al. 2016). A couple of Smart City scholars have attempted to integrate the Boyd Cohen's model of Smart City KPIs with the ISO-37120 with the corresponding indicators to simplify the metrics for measuring cities see for instance (Ceballos and Larios 2016). Section 4.3 discusses the KPI models in details.

2.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Measuring the Smartness of Cities and the Existing Smart City Wheels

The recent concerns on the need to identify metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) that can measure the impact of Smart City solutions and platforms in order to improve city smartness characteristics, through well-articulated performance indicators, is receiving stakeholders support. Many cities are transitioning from traditional cities into Smart Cities and a main motivation for this trend is because of their perceived ability to improve the standard of living of the people residing in such cities. However, in order to justify this assertion, it is necessary to identify some relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through which we can analyze their impact.

In a comparative study by Giffinger, Fertner et al. (2007), on the role of city-rankings in a regional competition focused on operationalising Smart Cities, they identified a comprehensive catalogue of indicators for measuring developments in medium-size cities of Europe. Drawing from their findings, the authors summarised the characteristics of a Smart City into six (6) major headings, namely Smart Economy, Smart People, Smart Governance, Smart Mobility, Smart Environment, and Smart Living. The study, which adopted the methodology of weighing the influence and importance of the factors or indicators, produced a framework model for analysing Smart Cities with thirty-three (33) factors described by a

number of indicators. Carli et al. (2013), in a similar framework for classifying performance indicators for measuring and managing the smartness of cities stressed further that to achieve the goal of making cities smarter, there is need to optimally and intelligently measure and monitor cities performance and analyse their competitiveness as well as evaluate their sustainability. Although the authors were of the view that there is no valid set of indicators for measuring performance of cities in each context and purpose, they proposed a novel two-dimensional framework (human and technological context) for classifying KPIs of a Smart City. This study also adopted the six (6) characteristics of Smart Economy, Smart People, Smart Governance, Smart Mobility, Smart Environment, and Smart Living in the framework to enable policy makers, planners and other stakeholders make intelligent decisions. Figure 4.1 highlights the six commonly used Smart City wheels proposed by Giffinger et al. (2007).

Smart Economy
Smart People
Smart Government
Smart Mobility
Smart Environment
Smart Living

Figure.1: Characteristics of Smart City
Source: (Giffinger et al., 2007)

The model and the framework were discussed using the above six (6) characteristics extensively. Cohen and Giffinger’s model are similar in terms of the six characteristics and ranking/benchmarking approaches. However, measuring the six characteristics without infrastructure as a core component could result in ignoring a major issue in the context of emerging economies since many of these countries struggle to put the proper infrastructure in place that will drive Smart Cities. Similarly, the framework proposed by Carli et al. (2013) succeeded in re-grouping the characteristics and the corresponding indicators into objective and subjective dimensions but the basic issue of identifying the core indicators for measuring the impacts of Smart City in line with common taxonomy was not addressed. This ignores the challenges of infrastructure provisioning in emerging cities.

In an attempt to further streamline the existing Smart City wheels and indicators, (Chowdhury and Dhawan 2016) introduced the Delphi method to evaluate the set of Smart Cities performance indicators established by ITU. Chowdhury and Dhawan’s model also characterised the key performance indicators for Smart Cities into six similar dimensions identifying Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Environmental Sustainability, Productivity, Quality of Life, Equity and Social Inclusion, and Physical Infrastructure with the corresponding parameters for measuring performance. The authors attempted to further split the six dimensions into measurable categories with a test case study using the Delphi review in India.

In contrast, Ceballos and Larios (2016), adopted a Kano model to provide empirical support in planning a Smart City using the Cohen’s model of KPIs with comprehensive integration of the 17 metrics of measurement models identified in ISO-37120. Ceballos and Larios’s principle proposes a Smart City investment model that encourages improved identity of the people with the city by prioritising their service needs in terms of investment in Smart City and quality of life. The study adopted the use case of CUCEA UDG living Lab –Guadalajara to validate the model. For further information on the integration of ISO-37120 model with Cohen’s model of Smart Cities, see Ceballos and Larios (2016).

Further, numerous academic literature addresses Smart City development from different perspectives of characterising the core components of Smart Cities while a host of others attempted to develop taxonomies that are based on the drivers. In this area, Nam and Pardo (2011) developed a framework based on three (3) core components discussed earlier: technology, people and institutions, both in terms of dimension and factors. In another example, Lee, Hancock et al. (2014) taxonomised the characteristics of Smart City based on technological and institutional elements well represented in six (6) taxonomies: urban openness, service innovation, partnerships formation, urban proactiveness, Smart City infrastructure integration and Smart City governance. It is imperative to suggest that Smart Infrastructure should form the core characteristic of Smart Cities. In this direction, the six characteristics can be summarised and discussed under three core dimensions of Smart City (i.e. Smart Infrastructure, Smart Institutions and Smart People).

This study explores the findings from available research results in view of the dynamic nature of this field in order to identify the major drivers of Smart Cities and the practical challenges before proposing a model for measuring the impacts. The paper therefore aims to provide a novel framework model for measuring smartness, factoring in the core indicators that can be universal and meeting the major challenges of an emerging economy using primary data.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR SMART CITY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Identifying appropriate performance indicators for measuring, managing, and monitoring the smartness of cities need to comply substantially with existing knowledge in the field of Smart City development. The imperative involves the development of a novel framework for measurement, but it goes beyond it to address the key challenges in detail. Building on existing knowledge in this field and the literature discussed earlier, this study identified three (3) core components of Smart Cities with comprehensive factors and key indicators to form the theoretical foundation to suggest a holistic view of metrics with which the KPIs of Smart Cities can be measured. The proposed core components include infrastructure, institution, and the people. Infrastructure is at the core of Smart City development. It is also the platform upon which Smart Economy, Smart Mobility, Smart Living and other dimensions introduced in the previous research are built.

In most emerging economies, cities are faced with the challenges of infrastructure provisioning (e.g. power, ICT, transport, water, etc.) that need to be measured. The factors and the specific indicators that drive the infrastructure component therefore need further consideration in order to produce an all-inclusive framework that can be adopted in an emerging economy. There is limited literature that explains infrastructure as a component in this manner; the proposed three dimensions of classifying Smart City factors and indicators are validated through a focus group exercise as summarised in the methodology. Table-1 presents the three (3) dimensional framework for measuring impacts of Smart City planning with more consideration for infrastructure as the foundation.

It is imperative to emphasise that the infrastructural performance of a city cannot be taken for granted because Smart Economy, effective management and the technological advancement that drives smartness in all dimensions depends on the existence of Smart infrastructure (Nam and Pardo 2011). Based on the focus group exercise, Smart Infrastructure, Smart Institutions, and Smart People were prioritized as the core components of Smart Cities upon which Smart

Economy can strive. In this arrangement, core factors/indicators for Smart living were considered very relevant to people hence, the three agreed core components were used to identify the core factors/indicators of Smart Cities that can conveniently be used to analyze similar indicators used in Europe and America depending on the peculiarity of the city.

Table 1. The Proposed Framework for Measuring Impacts of Smart City

Components	Factors	Indicators
Smart Infrastructure	Availability of smart grid/robust energy	Number of green energy sources and megawatts generated per inhabitant
		Rate of uninterrupted power available per inhabitant
	Availability of ICTs Infrastructure (source: ITU, 2014)	Number of mobile phone as % of city population
		Number of Internet access as % of city population
	Secured and innovative transport system (source: Giffinger et al, 2007)	Use of environmental friendly vehicles
		Number of autonomous vehicles
		Efficient transport network per inhabitant
	Availability of sustainable healthcare facilities (source: Giffinger et al, 2007)	Increased life expectancy
Number of hospital and hospital beds per inhabitant		
		Number of qualified doctors, nurses, and health attendants per inhabitant
Smart Institution	Environmental Sustainability (source: ITU, 2014)	Improved Air quality (CO, SO ₂ , NO ₂ reduction)
		Reduction in noise pollution
		Reduction in Greenhouse gas emission per capita
	Innovative and proactive security system	% reduction in crime rate
		Number of crime profiled in real-time
	Tourist potential (source: Giffinger et al, 2007)	Number of visitors to tourist centres
		Revenue generated in tourism as % of total revenue
	Entrepreneurship (source: Giffinger et al, 2007)	Increased number of new registered businesses
Increased number of innovation hubs		
Smart People	Creativity (source: Cohen, 2015)	Number of creative industries as % total industries
		Share of people working in creative industries
	Quality education (source: Giffinger et al, 2007)	Number of educated citizens at different levels of education
		Number of skilled citizen as % of city population
	Increased productivity (source: Cohen, 2015)	GDP as % of employed citizen
Ratio of employed to unemployed citizens		

The six commonly used Smart City wheels have been discussed in various Smart City scholarship, thus this paper will not dwell on the entire six wheels in the theoretical framework since previous efforts have sufficiently discussed them in different perspectives as highlighted in the literature review. Although in some of the literature, institutional

arrangements were discussed under organization and governance but the emphasis on institutional capabilities remain unchanged. This paper therefore considers the need to contribute to the research gap by focusing on infrastructure, institution, and the people as key components of Smart Cities where there is need to identify factors and indicators for measuring smartness especially in an emerging economy.

3.1 Smart Infrastructure

Most of the existing literature on Smart City discussed the issue of infrastructure with a focus on ICT infrastructure. Although the perception or the alignment of infrastructure component with ICT is understandable because of the critical role that ICT plays in making the dream of building a sustainable city a reality; in other instances, infrastructure is seen as technological infrastructure or techno-ware (Schaffers et al. 2011). In contrast, ICT infrastructure cannot be singled out as the most critical component in measuring the impact of Smart Cities in that ICT as a component of Smart City requires the existence of other infrastructure like energy (Smart Grid), utilities, safety, etc. In addition, Schaffers et al. (2011), discussed infrastructure from a different perspective with the dimension of ICT and utilities introducing the concept of smart transportation, mobility and parking, broadband, embedded systems, energy and savings/smart grid, environment monitoring and safety.

In supporting the position of infrastructure as a critical component of Smart Cities, Forrester (Washburn et al. 2009) posited that “*Smart City is a collection of Smart Computing technologies applied to the seven critical infrastructure components and services*”. The study further identified seven (7) critical infrastructure components of Smart City and services which include education, healthcare, administration, public safety, transportation, real estate, and utilities. The authors presented these critical infrastructure components with real-life examples to assist stakeholders in visualizing Smartness of cities.

Education: The metrics for quality education range from availability of digital content, improved access to online resources, low cost of educational programmes to technological platforms for collaboration since these are factors that need to be identified and properly classified for measurement.

Healthcare: The metrics include the availability of accurate diagnosis, patient records, and a platform for quick response to emergency services, knowledge sharing amongst health workers, tele-medicine facilities, and the existence of various platforms for remote medical services. These also have infrastructure components that need to be identified for measurement.

Public Safety: The police and other security agencies (e.g. fire service men) are now leveraging innovative technologies to improve response rate to emergencies and threats. In this area, Washburn et al. (2009) cited an example of a 911 real-time dashboard providing information on emergency needs that have helped New York City to reduce crime rate by 27% with the aid of closed circuit television (CCTV) and video analytics. The factors affecting the rate of response and the outcome as cited in the New York case can be classified and measured.

Transportation: The financial and environmental impacts of transportation in Smart Cities as well as reduction in the congestion can be measured. In this topic, Stockholm, Sweden as

cited in (Naphade et al. 2011), implemented a system equipped with lasers and cameras that automatically charge drivers on a “pay as you go” basis, thereby reducing gas emission and congestion. See Washburn et al. (2009) for details on utilities, real-estate, and administrative components of Smart Infrastructure. See also Naphade et al. 2011 for use case examples.

In order to arrive at workable KPIs for measuring impacts of Smart Cities, factors/indicators for measuring the critical areas/components of infrastructure need to be identified and classified accordingly.

3.2 Smart Institutions

In defining the Smart Institution as a core component of Smart Cities, a good number of authors stresses the quality of political strategies, availability of public services, support of government and policy for governance (see for instance Nam and Parado, 2011, Giffinger et al, 2007). Smart governance in this context refers to our concept of Smart Institution that leverage technologies (ICTs, sensors, RFID, etc) for efficient service delivery (see also Komninos 2009). Further, (chourabi et al 2012) also discussed extensively the component of Smart governance from the perspective of public-private partnership (PPP), leadership and effective collaboration for quality decision making. In summary, the Smart Institution includes all the essential factors of institutional arrangements that strive to ensure improved quality of life for the citizenry and availability of the entire factor in different perspectives of governance, sustainability, and few other dimensions that only differ in terms of terminology. Some of the core themes defining the Smart Institution component are summarised below:

Environmental Sustainability: Environmental Sustainability is one of the most important issues in the urban environment that affects the quality of life of the people. A couple of Smart City scholarship have also addressed the issues of environment as a major characteristic/dimension of Smart Cities see for instance (Giffinger et al. 2007, Cohen, 2015). The metrics for quality of environment in this case ranges from improved air quality, climate change (e.g. CO, NO₂, SO₂, etc.) to traffic flow which can be measured with the emergence of Big Data analytics even in real-time. In Europe for instance, research findings (Penza, Suriano et al. 2014) revealed that a couple of Smart City scholars are experimenting solutions for measuring air quality in cities in line with EU’s Air Quality Directive 2008/50/EC. Dealing with environmental sustainability therefore is a critical challenge that smarter institutions must address.

Entrepreneurship: For cities to attain smartness, they key performance indicators relating to how they are entrepreneuring are crucial and can be measured as part of the city’s image in maximizing their innovative spirit and creative potentials for global competitiveness. In this regards, access to innovation hubs/R&D as well as improved business environment are important parameters.

Productivity: Productivity parameters basically deal with measuring key performance indicators relating to income, trade balance at the city level, capital investment, job creation indices in both formal and informal sub-sectors of the city.

3.3 Smart People

In addition to the above two core components, the concept of Smart Cities includes the people as core components. The Smart People as a core component of Smart Cities have been addressed extensively in both academic journals and industry report within the domain of Smart Cities. The definition of people component stress the role of human capital and education in the innovative development in cities changing the patterns of citizen engagement to bottom-up rather than top-down (Batty, Axhausen et al. 2012). According to Glaeser (2005), one of the key characteristics of Smart Cities is the availability of a skilled workforce. Similarly, the transformation to Smart City environment entails capabilities for vibrant R&D (knowledge-base) driven by educational institutions for urban diversity, social inclusion, crime-free society, and a host of other societal values (Yigitcanlar et al. 2008). The component of “people” is further summarised as follows:

Quality of Life: WHO (1998) defines Quality of Life (QoL) as “individual perceptions of their position in life in the context of culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns”. In Smart Cities, improved quality of life of the people either in terms of emotional well-being, health status, financial status, and other aspects of life are of great concern. Quality of Life is beyond national GDP as measure of prosperity for national economies in the context of smart cities, it addresses key performance indicators relating to health, education, safety, and convenience (Chowdhury & Dhawan, 2016).

Equity and Social Inclusion: In Smart Cities, social cohesion is of utmost priority in city governance. Thus, the main concerns of equity and social inclusion parameters includes dealing with racial discrimination, gender inequalities, transparency (openness) and participatory system of governance. For instance, one of the major Smart City initiatives of Boston includes the Participatory China Town – A platform for public participation in policy making for urban planning (Chinatown 2017). The concept of Smart People is well discussed in a number of academic and industry-based Smart City journals (see for instance Giffinger et al, 2007, 2010). See also (Nam and Pardo, 2011, Edvinsson 2006).

4. METHODOLOGY

A systematic literature survey was conducted to elicit the knowledge required to meet the objective of this study. Current data on Smart City development and the key performance indicators for measuring smartness of a city were sourced from academic journals, reports from research institutions, and white papers of international/regional organisations in an effort to identify core indicators that are already being used as reference for Smart City impact assessment. The idea was to first generate a comprehensive list of factors/indicators based on the existing Smart City wheels and ISO-37120 resilient city standard for measuring the smartness of a city and subject these priority themes to a focus group to validate and refine the indicators for the purpose of analyzing them using Smart City stakeholders in Abuja. The focus group exercise started in Abuja from July 04, 2016 and was concluded July 20, 2016. Abuja was selected as a case study because the focus of this study is on emerging economies and FCT-Abuja had recently launched a vibrant campaign for smart growth (Jiriko, JY et al. 2015). Besides, Nigeria has been labelled an “emerging economy” in the league of the MINT nations i.e. Mexico, Indonesia, Nigeria and Turkey (Financier Worldwide Magazine 2014), (Akpan et al. 2014).

Recognizing the challenges of infrastructure deficit that still exist amongst the emerging economies, this research integrates from different sources of proposed KPI for Smart Cities and validates through 3-stages of focus group interviews. Firstly, from industry perspectives, secondly expert's opinion in academia, and finally from the urban development perspectives dominated by FCT Administration. To articulate the focus, the study received valid feedbacks from the stakeholders based on the core objectives of the research. Doing so, a good number of changes to the existing core components of Smart Cities were made for ease of analysis at the same time to address the perceived interrelationship while the factors/indicators were streamlined in line with the priority dimensions. For instance, the need for Smart Infrastructure was prioritized and it was considered as a core component of Smart City amongst the three categories of stakeholders in Abuja (an emerging city) instead of "Smart Economy" as emphasized in the existing models.

The focus group interview adopted an aspect of Q-methodology to elicit knowledge from "data-rich" stakeholders in a more scientific manner in order to remove the researcher's biasness (Stephenson 1953). In this procedure, the interview sessions were targeted at the top executives in core stakeholders organizations who were also asked to nominate experienced officers below the managerial cadre who are conversant with the Abuja Smart City initiative to participate in the ranking session. Prior to this, the key elements of the ISO-37120 resilient city standard and the proposed Smart City "wheels" retrieved from academic journals, industry reports, and standards were listed resulting in 29 components for consideration during the interviews with top executives. At the end of the interview phase, the list of components was pruned down to 18-components and transformed into statements for stakeholders to rank in line with their perception as well as priority Smart City themes that are relevant to the focus of the Abuja Smart City programme. The Q-methodology used in this study differ significantly from the usual Q-methodology that employ factor analysis (Uittenbroek et al. 2014). It also deviates a little from qualitative Q-methodology (de Wijs et al., 2016) such that a set of statements (Q-set) that need to be ranked were generated with an empty space for participants to name their own priority theme not mentioned in the comprehensive list (set) and rank them accordingly as shown in figure-2.

Figure.2: Q-Methodology Template for Ranking.

As summarized in Table-2, 15 experts representing 7 professionals from the ICT industry, 3 scholars from the academia, and 5 urban planners from FCT Administration participated in the Q-Methodology ranking exercise. Based on the composition of the professionals that participated in this exercise, IT Experts tends to outnumber other professions and this bears to the understanding of the top executives who did the nominations in line with their own perception of the Smart City concept. In addition, most of the participants nominated by the stakeholder organisations were at some points involved in the Nigerian Smart City Initiative stakeholders committee except one participant from a private university, which explains their level of awareness. For instance, none of the participants from ICT industry organisations and the academia were of transport background.

consensus were reached amongst the participants that adequate investment in the infrastructural component is needed to support the smart aspiration of FCT-Abuja as summarised in figure-3. Although several Smart City KPI models focus on Smart Economy, Smart Living, Smart Safety and a host of others; participants in this study perceived these categories of Smart City characteristics as important but emphasized the need to focus on the core components of infrastructure, institution, and people with core indicators that cut-across the supporting components for ease of management.

5.2 Smart Institution

The second component also ranked very high in this exercise is the Smart Institution. As noted in the literature review, for Smart Cities to improve entrepreneurial growth, improve city administration for quality of life of the citizen and so on, they require smarter institutions that will manage all governance issues. In which case, they will promote productivity (job creation), efficiency, sustainability (air quality and climate change), improved access to innovation hubs/R&Ds. In all the focus group interviews and Q-methodology ranking exercise with the stakeholders, the need for smarter institutions that will drive the smart initiatives in all sectors of the city is high on the agenda. As shown in figure-3, there was consensus in ranking by the participants confirming the positions of the interviewees that smarter institution is a priority and one of the most important components for all the group of stakeholders.

Interestingly, participants from the academia and their counterparts in urban planning agreed with the views of the “industry” participants on the three core components highlighted above but a couple of participants from these two groups considered the component of environment as very important theme in FCT-Abuja Smart City project. As shown in figure-3, the component of environment is regarded as one the popular priority areas for this group. This position largely aligns with the views of some of the interviewees who emphasized the need to identify the core indicators of environment as important indicators that smarter institutions can address. Specifically, these participants (academia/urban planning) highlighted the factors of “environmental pollution” and “environmental protection” as key issues for Smarter Abuja.

5.3 Smart People

Finally, the third priority component for Abuja Smart City stakeholders is the Smart People. This component as summarised in the literature review represents the social capital in Smart City initiatives. As shown in figure-3, the participants expressed in strong terms the central role of the people component during the ranking and interview exercise. Again, one of the interviewees in the academia group suggested that Smart City deployment in Abuja should start from serious investment in the people component in order to develop adequate human capacity that will drive the innovation and knowledge exchange in the envisioned smarter environment in the capital city of Abuja.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The importance of Smart Cities has been discussed and the social innovations that they bring and the impact that this has on the cities where they are implemented have been identified. An analysis of the KPIs that have been used to quantify the impact of Smart Cities in prior research has been carried out. Although this is an ongoing research, the immediate findings revealed that most KPIs took it for granted that the host cities already have the adequate infrastructure to support the deployment of Smart Cities.

This condition holds true in many developed countries but the dearth of appropriate infrastructure in developing countries makes a case for a review of the KPIs with a view to ensuring that the infrastructure challenge takes centre stage. The result of this work is the development of infrastructure-centric KPIs that can be readily used for assessing the impact of Smart Cities. With many cities around the globe adopting the concept of Smart City, it has become imperative to proactively identify the critical factors and indicators that will be useful to both developed and emerging economies for measuring how the smartness of a city impacts on its environment and citizens.

In the future, the conceptual framework will be used to conduct surveys covering larger stakeholder groups with a view to use the result of the empirical evidence in proposing a Smart City model based on the identified indicators for assessing the impacts of Smart Cities.

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